

TERMINOLOGICAL EMBODIMENT IN DIPLOMACY.

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The article is focused on the study of the origins of English diplomatic terminology. Particular attention is given to its dual nature, in the sense that it includes elements of purely English origin, as well as terms borrowed from other European languages. The study provides evidence that borrowed elements constitute its core and are crucially involved in the formation of the special diplomatic communication style.

Keywords: Gallicism, diplomatic terminology, diplomatic text, Latinism, loan-word, the term.

Introduction

Communication between or among nations is impossible without diplomacy. Diplomatic communication has a long history and has always been crucial in forging and maintaining international relations. The language of diplomacy is a reflection of this long history. Its distinctiveness lies in the careful selection of words and phrases, terminological loading, scrupulous choice of syntactic constructions. The organization of language into special repetitive patterns occurred over the course of centuries in the process of cementing relationships between people and nations.

The objective of our work is twofold: firstly, to document and describe diplomatic language and the terminology inherent within it which is the result of language choices made within English diplomatic discourse, and to demonstrate the

origins of its key terms. In doing so, this paper fills what might be considered to have been a gap in terms of research relating to diplomatic terminology.

To achieve a comprehensive investigation we have used methods of complex and combinatory linguistic analysis: contextual analysis, which enabled us to study the realization of meanings by the use of particular terms; statistical analysis, which enabled us to perform quantitative evaluations; and the method of structural and semantic modeling, which served as the basis for carrying out a classification of terms. The material for the investigation is the terminology found in diplomatic documents (agreements, pacts, speeches, treaties, etc) and catalogued in dictionaries which provide a documentation of diplomatic language (partly presented in references).

1. The Origins of Diplomatic Terminology.

1.1. General Remarks.

The most ancient example of diplomatic language can be found in a peace and friendship treaty concluded around 2400 B.C., which was originally in the Royal Library of Ebla, but now is housed in the Archaeological Museum of Damascus. Today, in these times of democracy we may find the same idea, conveyed in the same terms: "His Majesty the King of Belgians ,... .. Her royal Highness the Grand Duchess of Luxembourg, her Majesty the Queen of the Netherlands" [9, p. 3]. The examples mentioned above testify to the fact that the language of diplomacy has not changed much. According to F. Matos, diplomatic language can be described as a "peace-building, peace-making and peace-promoting force" [7, p. 283].

The expression "diplomatic language" is used to denote three different things. In its first sense it signifies the actual language (whether it is Spanish, French, or English) which is employed by diplomats in correspondence or negotiations. In its second sense it refers to set phrases which over the course of centuries have become part of the ordinary diplomatic vocabulary. In its third, and most common, sense it is used to describe that selected form of language which enables diplomats to express

complicated or potentially controversial ideas without being either offensive or impolite.

Loan-words constitute the core of English diplomatic language. As Nataliya N. Rayevskaya points out, a study of loan-words is not only of etymological interest. Words give us valuable information with respect to life in the nations involved. Loan words have justly been called the milestones of philology [8, p. 10].

The etymological aspect of this investigation is important, since it is widely known that certain insights into the current usage of a term can be gained from a full knowledge of the term's history, and that a better understanding of terms can be achieved by learning how words are related to other words in English and to words in other languages.

This study deals with borrowed terminology, functioning in English diplomatic discourse, including both so-called loan terms from other sublanguages and loan-words from other languages. It is essential for the purposes of this study to define the term, as it is the object of the investigation.

We propose to investigate borrowed terminology which is employed in English diplomatic discourse in terms of both its composite and its historical aspects.

1.2. The Composite Aspect of Borrowings: The Limits of a Terminological System.

Much of the language of diplomatic discourse is a matter of "common form". This "common form" can be viewed from two different perspectives. The first one is the composite aspect of investigation in connection with which we should mention that diplomatic lexicon is a mixture of different terminologies, primarily juridical and economic. It is a common linguistic tendency that during the development and mutual updating of the lexical systems, terms from various areas of knowledge tend to interfere with each other due to the process of integration. A terminological "system" is an aggregation of terms which are both specifically connected and interdependent. It is a complex ensemble of language units which

express specific concepts and which are associated with the theory and practice of a specific branch of knowledge. Diplomatic terminology is an essential element of diplomatic discourse and expresses its inherent concepts, setting it apart from discourses with other cognitive and communicative objectives. The system of terms and the system of basic vocabulary words form the sublanguage of a certain branch of scientific knowledge.

Sometimes it is difficult to identify the boundary between a legal and a diplomatic text, or to state definitely to what sublanguage a certain term belongs. Moreover, there are many terms that are no longer confined to just one terminological system (such as "NATO", "status quo", and "terrorism"). Terms such as these could equally be associated with the sublanguages of the military, of diplomacy or of sociopolitics. It should be also pointed out that juridical and economic terms have always played a special role in the formation of the diplomatic sublanguage; moreover, they were usually the source from which its elements were drawn, since the very first issues of international life were those involving trade and law.

1.3. The Historical Aspect of Borrowings: A Brief Overview.

The other perspective that justifies the "common form" of English diplomatic language involves the historical aspect of the investigation in the course of which we have found that diplomatic language is, from a historical point of view, a sublanguage consisting of words drawn from a variety of different languages. To obtain a confirmation of this and to fully appreciate the nature of diplomatic terminology we need to get acquainted with its history.

There is no definitive answer to the question of how diplomatic language and its terminology came to be what it is. Much of the explanation can be found in the historical events which have left their mark on the language of English diplomacy.

Non-assimilated loan-words within English diplomatic communication can be viewed as forming a part of the language standards. We suggest the use of this term

to define a special type of diplomatic terminology that provides unambiguous understanding and interpretation of situations and concepts touched upon in documents (such as “on behalf of”, “terms and conditions”, “null and void”, “any and all”). We postulate their importance in the language of diplomacy, in that they are ready-made formulas which make the process of communication easier. Latin and French non-assimilated borrowings constitute a special subset with the standard vocabulary of diplomatic language. However, their frequency of usage is not the same in all genres of diplomatic communication. They mostly occur in verbal notes, working documents of sessions, and treaties. We suggest that in order of the frequency of occurrence of Latinisms and Gallicisms legal documents are in first place; economic texts in second place; political texts in third place; technical matter in fourth place; and documents concerning the environment are in fifth place.

3. The Role of French in Diplomatic Terminological System Formation

Having now considered the important place which Latin holds in terms of our present study, we can turn our attention to other languages which can be regarded as contributors to English diplomatic terminology. Not surprisingly, French is by a large margin the most important other source of general vocabulary, and of diplomatic terminology in particular. Interestingly, this phenomenon was not part of a long and gradual process of infiltration: instead, it was a direct result of the conquest of England by William of Normandy. After the Norman Conquest, a process began whereby English was replaced by French in documents and indeed in all aspects of life. For the centuries the language of official documents was French. Moreover, it maintained its status as England’s diplomatic language. Starting from 1417 most of England’s official documents were written in English. For some time French and Latin coexisted in the domain of international life.

As a result of these and some later historical events, English assimilated many borrowings from French in the sphere of diplomacy, such as: prison, schedule, alias, sentence, jurisdiction, sentence, embassy, ambassador, sabotage, envoy, diplomat,

state, war, money, victory, government, parliament, justice, army, contract, and policy. Soon French became the language confined to the diplomatic profession. Gallicisms retain their original French form, partly because of the fact that their use is hermetically confined to the sphere of diplomacy, contrary to Latinisms, most of which occur in discourses other than diplomatic. French set expressions help to create the special style of diplomatic language, where politeness is closely interwoven with rituality.

Conclusions

First of all, we may conclude that two languages, Latin and French, have made the greatest contribution to the English diplomatic word-stock. Second, borrowings functioning in English diplomatic discourse are of two types, assimilated and non-assimilated. They both contribute a great deal to the development of the special ritualistic style of documents. Third, legal, economic, and military terms, as well as terms from other sublanguages used in diplomatic texts constitute the periphery of the diplomatic terminological field and their usage in English diplomatic discourse is dictated by the correlation between economics, jurisprudence, diplomacy and other spheres of life, as well as by their close logical connection.

This integration of languages and terminologies, as well as the diversity of the borrowings, results in a special type of text and intercourse, defined as English diplomatic discourse where rituality and conservatism are of great importance in maintaining diplomatic contacts between nations.

Just as it might be possible to underestimate the importance of diplomacy and diplomatic initiatives when studying the course of human history, it might likewise be possible to underestimate the role of the specialized language that has evolved over the course of centuries, which provides diplomats and leaders of nations with a vehicle for dealing with many delicate and portentous matters of mutual concern in the affairs of countries great and small. In view of this, we feel that our study of some of the precise aspects that were and are involved in the formation of diplomatic

language is a subject that has relevance and significance, and which provides some insights that could have far-reaching ramifications for the future development of diplomacy.

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